

**THE MAIN OBJECTIVE OF THE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY IS
RESPECT FOR HUMAN DIGNITY**

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Abstract. The role of a lawyer is very important in protecting the rights and interests of a person. One of the main tasks today is a radical increase in the efficiency of the advocacy. The Development Strategy for 2022-2026 provides for 100 goals in 7 areas, and this article is devoted to the institution of advocacy, which is one of the most pressing issues. In addition, this article emphasizes that one of the main directions is to increase human dignity and further develop a free civil society, and most importantly, the transformation of the principles of justice and the rule of law into a fundamental and necessary condition for the development of the country. Thus, proposals are presented on creating conditions for the implementation and expansion of the rights of a lawyer to protect the rights and legitimate interests of a person, equalizing the procedural possibilities of prosecution and defense based on the principle of disputability at all stages of criminal proceedings. Therefore, the issue of expanding the rights of a lawyer in determining whether the adversarial

principle also applies to pre-trial proceedings. To improve the criminal procedure legislation on some problems of this institution, scientific, theoretical, and practical recommendations are given on the mechanism for implementing the priority tasks set in the development strategy.

Keywords: strategy, human rights, defense, attorney, court, law enforcement agencies, free legal aid, attorney's warrant an attorney's assistant.

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In the development strategy for 2022-2026, 100 goals have been set in 7 directions, and at its core lies the important idea of "a society where human value is a priority and a people-friendly state". On the basis of this noble goal set by the head of our state, our people are becoming the real authors of new reforms. In this regard, the principle "From Action Strategy to Development Strategy" is aimed at creating the necessary political-legal, socio-economic and scientific-educational basis for the reforms to be implemented in our country in the next five years. Building a people-friendly state through further development of a free civil society based on the directions defined in the draft development strategy, and turning the principles of justice and the rule of law into the most basic and necessary condition for development in our country is one of the important directions.

In order to make the principles of justice and the rule of law the most basic and necessary condition for development in our country, 28 measures aimed at achieving

the following goals are defined: ensuring reliable protection of property rights and illegal decision (action) imposing the obligation to prove in court that it is not on the official ("presumption of innocence") [1]; to further simplify the system of registration of citizens by place of residence ("propiska") and to create additional convenience for the population, instead of taking the citizen to the internal affairs department for verification, the procedure for checking all information on the spot introduction; to consistently continue the policy of liberalizing criminal legislation, to introduce a system of providing "initial social and material assistance packages" to return those who have served their sentence to society and implement a business project; establishing effective judicial control over the activities of state bodies and officials through the development of administrative justice; forming a new image of law enforcement agencies, directing their activities to serve the interests of the people and ensure the rights and freedoms of citizens; attention was paid to the issues of fundamentally increasing the capacity of the advocacy institute to protect human rights, freedoms and legal interests, and ensuring its institutional independence.

Relevance of the study

One of the most urgent goals mentioned above is the improvement of the bar institute. The role of a lawyer is important in the protection of human rights and interests. Today, the International Bar Association, which unites more than 80,000 lawyers and more than 200 lawyers' associations and more than 170 legal societies, supports the independent practice of lawyers without external interference. The fact that he set himself the goal of support also indicates the attention paid to the profession of lawyer all over the world.

The creation of conditions for the implementation and expansion of lawyer's rights [2] serves to protect human rights and legal interests. At this point, it should be said that today many efforts are being made to expand the rights of lawyers in our republic. In particular, it is of urgent importance to create sufficient conditions for lawyers to have the necessary legal space for their professional activities and to have equal opportunities with the prosecution [3] in criminal proceedings. It is known that at all stages of the criminal process [4], the procedural possibilities of the prosecution and the defense parties are equalized based on the principle of dispute. Accordingly, it is appropriate to expand the rights of the lawyer in order to establish that the principle of dispute applies to the case before the court.

Material and methods

In the study, legal norms and scientific and theoretical views of legal scholars were used on the issues of further improvement of the legal profession institution from the point of view of further expansion of the lawyer's participation in the criminal proceedings.

The comparative legal method, analysis, synthesis and other methods were used during the research.

Research results

Raising the improvement of the human rights protection system to a new level, reliable protection of the rights and freedoms of the individual, increasing the authority [5] and procedural status [6] of lawyers at all stages of criminal proceedings, courts and law enforcement bodies - s [7] and measures aimed at ensuring the protection of citizens' rights and interests [8] in the activities of control bodies, and strengthening citizens' confidence in the law enforcement system are

being implemented consistently. No. PF-5441 dated May 12, 2018 "On measures to fundamentally increase the efficiency of the Bar Institute and expand the independence of lawyers", dated August 10, 2020 "Protection of the rights and freedoms of the individual in judicial investigation activities" Decree No. PF-6041 of December 13, 2019, "On measures to further strengthen the guarantees of the implementation of Great attention is being paid to the implementation of the tasks defined in the decision PQ-4551 "On measures to improve culture".

Based on the many adopted decrees and laws, it can be said that today there is a need to further systematize legal documents related to the activity of the bar and develop a directly applicable law. According to the Law on Advocacy, a number of requirements [9] are imposed on the lawyer. Currently, 2 years of work experience in a legal specialty is required to obtain a lawyer's license. It's time to introduce additional changes to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On improving the procedure for licensing legal activities and establishing legal entities." Let's touch on another issue: currently 60% of lawyers are over 50 years old. There are very few young people under the age of 30 in this field. This is definitely a problematic issue. Today, based on the population, it is important to increase the number of lawyers [10] from the number of highly qualified specialists. For young people to enter this field, it is appropriate to cancel the requirement of 2 years of legal experience from among the qualification requirements. Also, it is necessary to create an opportunity for persons with a higher legal education to pass the bar exam after 3 months of internship and to be allowed to pass the exam to get a bar license without passing the internship. Another issue: we believe that the introduction of the procedure for issuing a lawyer's license

through the "License" information system based on the decision of the higher or regional qualification commission will be effective.

Analysis of research results

Also, bachelor's and master's students have a great interest in studying practice as a lawyer's assistant in their spare time. Bachelor's students provide free legal advice and assistance to citizens in drafting and formalizing claims. Based on this, we can say that giving the right to work as a lawyer's assistant to the students of the bachelor's course of the higher legal education institutions in their free time will serve to increase the number of young lawyers in the future.

Also, on the basis of the Development Strategy, by introducing modern information technologies to advocacy activities, putting an end to excessive bureaucracy and red tape, eliminating the exchange of electronic documents with courts, law enforcement agencies and other state bodies. Putting in l is the same term.

Conclusions

The development strategy includes the introduction of a system to ensure the resolution of all legal consequences within the scope of a specific case, regardless of their relevance to the court, and to send applications to the competent court, in order to widely implement the principle of "single window" in the court system. xtab, this issue will save citizens from unnecessary hassles. It is also important to provide free lawyers to persons in need of social protection in administrative and civil cases. The reason is that when a citizen applies to the court [11] on an issue [12], his appeal [13] is not ignored.

It is known that in the second part of Article 87 of the Code of Criminal Procedure,

the lawyer's right to gather evidence is strengthened. However, the fact that the defense is not indicated among the persons determining the information considered as evidence in part 1 of Article 81 of the Criminal Procedure Code, which is called "types of evidence", can be considered as the advantage of the prosecution. In this regard, we believe that expanding the powers of the lawyer [15] in the procedural legislation [14] to collect and present evidence will further increase the weight of the defense side.

Also, the creation of the "Legal Assistance" electronic system, which ensures the exchange of documents between lawyers, courts, law enforcement bodies and other state bodies, and the introduction of the "Electronic Attorney's Warrant", which simplifies the participation of a lawyer in the process. serves to simplify criminal proceedings. One of the main issues is the implementation of the system of providing free legal aid to citizens in need of social protection at the expense of the state, in addition to criminal cases, civil and administrative cases, which confirms that citizens are protected by the state.

In short, improving the legal documents of the criminal procedure by further strengthening the status of the lawyer and developing norms regulating the mechanism of its activity is considered one of the urgent tasks of today.

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